

FABRICATION, AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LEDIPASVIR CARRIER METALLIC NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

The drug-delivery system based on nanostructured permits the development of new area for the transport and measured release of the drug molecules in the complicated diseased environment with limited side effects to the normal tissues of the living systems. The present study focused on the fabrication of the nano-carrier drug delivery system based on biocompatible molecules to increase the stability and strength of the ledipasvir. The Zinc and copper metals were selected due to their intrinsic biological application for synthesizing drug loaded metallic nanoparticles. The characteristics peaks for ZnNPs and CuNPs was achieved on 325nm and 260nm respectively by ultra-violet visible spectroscopy and in the finger print region of infra-red spectra which confirms the synthesis of nanoparticles. The % drug encapsulation value was found to be 16.17 for CuNPs and 35.72% for ZnNPs. The shape and size of synthesized nanoparticle was resolute by SEM and AFM. Simultaneous TGA-DSC analysis was conducted to study the kinetic and thermal parameters of encapsulated nanoparticles. The drug encapsulated CuNPs starts to degrade at 410°C which depicted the more thermal sustainability whereas ZnNPs is thermally labile but have more purity as sharp endothermic peak was observed in the DSC curve. The kinetic parameters were calculated by Horowitz-Metzger equation.

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis C (HC) has been globally recognized as the basic reason of chronic liver disorders last from its discovery i.e. 1989 [1]. This chronic infection followed to liver cirrhosis and hepato-cellular carcinoma which eventually leads to patient's death [2]. The 200 million people which becomes the 3 percent of total world population are suffering from HC [3]. HC is basically divided into six- genotypes [4] which resulted due to the highest error occurrence during the Hepatitis C virus replication of RNA-dependent RNA polymerases step of its life-cycle [5]. Among them equivalent to 83.4 million people are infected by

genotype 1 which has the highest rate among all the other genotypes infection [6]. Literature documented the various reason for the occurrence of HC infection but among them the contaminated blood and its product transfusion, abusive drug usage, blood dialysis procedure and transplantation of body organ are documented as of main concern [7]. It is becoming the threatening condition for all over the world as there is no as such vaccine available for prevention and more over the available treatments plans also have some deadly side effects. Conventionally it has been treated with PEG-interferon injections and ribavirin

for the duration of 48 weeks but it fails in curing the 40% of the infected patient but moreover the cost of the treatment is high, and has the severe adverse effects. [5]. The development of direct acting antiviral (DAA) is the major innovation in the treatment plan of HC [8, 9]. In 2015 FDA have approved a combination therapy based on Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir for the treatment of genotype 1 HC which have the most prevalence rate among all the other genotypes [10, 11] but it also has some drawback such as relapse of the disease, insufficient efficacy has been observing in the cirrhosis and fibrosis HC patients and undesirable side effects [12] which arises the need to develop the new approaches specially by using the nanotechnology to developed the targeted drug delivery system, sustained drug release and reducing the side effects of this newly developed DAA class.

Nano-medicine can be synthesized by transforming the larger drug molecules into the nanoparticles form or they can be transformed to nanostructure with or without the usage of any carrier materials [13]. The drug molecules mainly can be administered to the human body via oral, intravenous and subcutaneous route then it circulated with in the all body organ with the aid of blood circulation and accumulated to the targeted site in an optimum concentration for producing the therapeutic action [14]. However, the required action may not be achieved because of some drawback in the physico-chemical properties of the conventional drug molecules like shorter half-life, high dose amount and frequency, less selective, producing adverse effect on healthy tissues and experienced the multidrug-resistance. Moreover, considerable number of marketed drug molecules have experienced aqueous solubility issues which created the hindrance in the absorption to the intestine and also inhibited the circulation of drug by intravenous route of administration [15]. For overcoming these issues solubilizing agents or surfactant have been using during the formulation step but they also have some side effects such as neurotoxicity or other toxicities. FDA had approved first nano-medicine in 1990 and after that 24 more nano-medicine have been marketed up till now as by this strategy not only the drawbacks have been answered but also money and time is being saving because nano-medicine require roughly \$20-\$50 million and 3-4 years which is considerably less than

the required amount and time (\$500 million and over 10 years) for discovering a new drug candidate molecule [16, 17].

The nanoparticles show unique physicochemical characteristics which effect the biological actions of drugs. These distinctive characters of nanoparticles owe to its larger surface area and quantum effects, as of result of these character the reactivity, electrical behavior and their strength is to be improved in comparison with their larger molecules. The nano-sized structure of nanoparticles make them effective at cellular or subcellular [18, 19]. Targeted drug delivery is the core area of nanoparticles in drug delivery system [20]. So as the perfect nanoparticles should reach, identify, bind and transfer its encapsulated drug to specific pathological area and treat the infection at specific cellular and sub-cellular level by minimizing the undesirable action to other tissue organs [21-24]. The bottom-up methodology has been particularly used for the synthesis of nano-medicine whereby engineered larger molecule interact with each other upon peripheral stimuli and form nano-complex unit which was follow by loading of drug [25]. The nanoparticles of inorganic materials have wide range of applications in numerous disciplines like as chemicals [26], medicine [27] and imaging [28]. That's why it becomes a fascinating field to Pharma-researcher due to its distinctive size dependent physical parameter (magnetic, optical, catalytic and electronic) which gives sustainability, huge surface area, tenable composition, multi-functionality, monitored release, selective binding, less chances of developing resistance, collective action and greater strength to drugs in contrast to conventional drug moiety [29, 30].

1. Experimental

1.1. Material and Instrument

All chemical solvents, metal salt (Zinc chloride anhydrous, powder, $\geq 99.995\%$ and Copper (I) chloride $\geq 99.995\%$ trace metals basis) were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co, USA and were used as received. The Ledipasvir was a gifted sample from Atco-laboratories limited- Pakistan. The UV-visible spectrum was recorded in the range of 200 to 800nm by UV-1800 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were observed in the range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} by Thermo- Nicolet

Avatar 330 FT-IR. SEM images was carried out by SEM, JSM-6380A, JEOL, Japan and detection was performed by EDS, EX-54175iMU, JEOL, Japan. AFM images was carried out by Agilent technologies 5500 atomic force microscope with silicon nitride probe at 298.563 kHz resonance frequency. TGA-DSC scan was taken by Simultaneous Thermal Analyser- DSC+TGA.

1.2. Methodology

1.2.1. Synthesis of Metallic Nanoparticles

Accurately weight zinc chloride and sodium hydroxide in the ratio of 1:4 and dissolve in freshly prepared distilled water in a separate flask by keeping on hot plate for continuous stirring until the homogenous solution was obtained. Add drop wise NaOH solution to ZnCl solution which was followed by addition of methanol with continuous stirring over the hotplate. White precipitate of Zinc oxide nanoparticles is obtained which than filtered and place under vacuum desiccator for complete drying of the solvents. Accurately weigh the amount of copper chloride and dissolve in 27% ammonia solution into the 10ml of volumetric flask. Add 5% HCl solution to neutralize the pH of the solution which is followed by the addition of 100ml of 0.25M sodium borohydrate solution which contain starch as a stabilizing agent. Dark brown precipitate of copper oxide nanoparticles was obtained which was filtered and dried under vacuum desiccator.

1.2.2. Encapsulation of Ledipasvir to Metallic Nanoparticles

Firstly, prepared the metallic and drug solution having strength of 0.2M and 10mM respectively. Transfer the metallic solution to the flask and kept on stirring for 5 minutes and then add drug solution drop wise in the ratio of 20:1 which was stirred at 1200 rpm for 180 minutes at room temperature.

The solution was kept un-disturbed for 24 hours and after that take out the supernatant solution for UV-scanning.

Drug encapsulation is calculated by following formula.

$$\% \text{ of drug encapsulation} = \frac{[a - b]}{a} * 100$$

Here “a-b”= concentration of drug in nano-medicine and “a” = remaining concentration of drug in the solution [25, 31].

1.2.3. Characterization

The characterization of the synthesized metallic nanoparticles and nano-medicine is done UV-Visible spectroscopy, SEM, AFM, FTIR, DSC-TGA and kinetic parameters are calculated by Horowitz-Metzger equation which is given below.

$$\log \left[\log \frac{W_f}{W_f - W} \right] = \frac{\alpha \cdot E^*}{2.303RT_s^2} - \log 2.303$$

In the above equation W_f is equivalent to overall mass loss on completion of decomposition reaction, at temperature T mass loss equals to W, R equivalent to universal gas constant, T_s is equivalent to highest temperature of reaction and α is equivalent to the alteration of T- T_s .

The activation energy can be calculated from the $\text{slope} = \frac{E^*}{2.303RT_s^2}$ of graph plotted between $\log[-\ln(1-\alpha)]$ and T- T_s .

2. Result and Discussion

Literature revealed that nanoparticles of various inorganic metals such as silver, gold and copper have been used for the biological activities and among them the essential traces elements which are present in various body organ like zinc and copper have attained much attention due to their excellent bio-compatibility, less toxic and economically cheap to other metals [32-36]. The present study is design to fabricate the stable and more therapeutic active nano-medicine for HC genotype 1 in comparison to LED by utilizing the intrinsic potential of antiviral properties of bio-compatible inorganic metals i.e. zinc and copper [37, 38]

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of Ledipasvir encapsulated Metallic Nanoparticles

ZnNPs was synthesized in good yield by the series of chemical reaction which involve firstly hydrolysis of zinc chloride into Zinc and Chloride ions and then the electrons in the

oxygen atoms forms the hydroxyl groups (-OH) of alcohol molecules bond with the zinc ions which results in the development of zinc oxide nano-material. The complete equation of the reaction is as follows.

CuNPs is synthesized by chemical reduction method which involves firstly the generation of ions by reacting with ammonium solution to given ammonium chloride and Cu ions which than further reduced to its nanoparticles state by reacting with sodium borohydrate's solution and starch was used as a capping agent for inhibiting the aggregation and oxidation of nanoparticles to enhance its stability.

2.1.1. UV-Visible spectroscopy

The synthesis protocols of zinc oxide nano-material were started by direct mixing of NaOH and ZnCl₂ solutions followed by addition of methyl alcohol. The UV-spectrum shows that the absorbance value is low and a red-shift is

observed in the wavelength related to the characteristic peak which correspond to the formation of aggregated NPs so as to get a small and non-aggregated NPs the solution of ZnCl₂ and NaOH solutions was firstly stirred on a hot plate for 10 minutes and then slowly add NaOH solution to ZnCl₂ solution which was further stirred for 5 minutes then followed by drop-wise addition of methanol with the help of burette. The white precipitate gets started to observe after addition of methanol i.e. the naked eye indication of fabrication of Zinc oxide nanoparticles. By adopting this optimized method, the symmetrical UV-peak is detected which confirm the fabrication of small and non-aggregated NPs. The stability of the synthesized NPs is checked by measuring the absorbance on day 1, 4 and 11th day. There is no variation observed in the height and shape of the peak other than the un-optimized method in which on day 11 the peak is just about to disappear (figure 1).

Figure 1 UV-spectra indicating synthesis and stability of ZnNPs

The fabrication of CuNPs was started by making the neutralized ammonium solution of CuCl₂ by addition of HCl. The formation of light blue color precipitate is the marker for neutralized solution. The reduction of copper to its nanoparticles form is performed by addition of starch-stabilized sodium borohydrate solution. The NaBH₄ solution was initially prepared in the volumetric flask, as on addition of NaBH₄ to the starch it get started to

bubble out vigorously, so some of the solution was needed to drain out which results into the in-complete addition of it to copper solution for reduction to dark brown precipitates of CuNPs. However, it was observed that the reaction get reverse after the 3 hours as brown precipitate again converted to blue color solution at room temperature which is the naked eye indication of un-stability of fabricated CuNPs. During the optimization process the starch stabilized solution is prepared in a large beaker and NaBH₄ is added with

continuous stirring with the help of glass rod and then this solution completely added drop wise to neutralized copper solution resulted in to the

fabrication of symmetrical and stabilized CuNPs as this time perpetual dark brown precipitate is achieved which is also confirm by UV-spectra (figure 2).

Figure 2 UV-spectra indicating synthesis and stability of CuNPs

2.1.2. Drug encapsulation

There are various metallic nanoparticles which have intrinsic biological activities so encapsulating the macro-drug molecules to the nanoparticles not only the physico-chemical properties of the drug are enhanced but its therapeutic action can also be improved which also decreases the dosage and frequency of administration of the drug to human body and limited its side effects. Drug encapsulation to metallic nanoparticles was attained by mixing the drug and NPs solution in the ratio of 20:1 for 1200 rpm speed for 180 minutes which was left undisturbed for 24 hours for maximum drug encapsulation to the metallic nanoparticles. On the next day centrifugation is performed to separate the drug encapsulated nanoparticles.

The drug encapsulated percentage was found to be 35.72% and 16.17% for zinc and copper nanoparticles respectively which is considered as high drug encapsulation value as up till now maximum of the reported nano-medicine have drawback of low drug encapsulated percentage which is generally less than of 10% with higher percentage of the carrier molecule. This draw back can be overcome by using inert porous material such as metal organic framework as metal ions and organic ligand complex have high drug encapsulation tendency due to the presence of larger surface area, excellent physiochemical properties for circulation and usage of biological metal as they have less toxicity and inert medicinal activities like as of drug candidate [13].

Figure 3 Drug encapsulation to metallic nanoparticles

2.1.3. SEM

The images of scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6380A, JEOL, Japan at x 27,000) was captured to study the peripheral morphology of the synthesized metallic nanoparticles which was prepared by sol-gel and chemical reduction method. It is shown in the images that the size of the blank and drug encapsulated metallic nanoparticles is smaller than 120nm so as we can conclude that the metallic salts are successfully converted into metallic oxide nanoparticles. After the drug loading images shows slight increase in size i.e. 4nm and 10nm for zinc and copper nanoparticles respectively, which resulted due to the slighter aggregation of nanoparticles during the drug loading process (figure 4).

Figure 4 SEM images of LED and metallic nano-medicine

2.1.4. ATR-FTIR

ATR-FTIR spectra of pure metallic nanoparticle was recorded in solid state. The observed spectra have all the characteristic peaks for the metallic oxide nanoparticles which confirm the fabrication and purity of the synthesized nanoparticles. The sharp peak near 500cm^{-1} have been observed in the zinc oxide nanoparticles scan which confirm its synthesis moreover there is no halide peak observed which predicted that

all the precursor salt has been successfully reduced to its nanoparticles. The IR-scan of copper nanoparticles have also predicted the synthesis as the stretching band of CuO bond at 530cm^{-1} is clearly seen. The other two characteristic peaks at 590 and 654cm^{-1} are also observed which confirm the purity of the synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles (figure 5).

Figure 5 IR-spectrum of metallic nanoparticles

2.1.5. AFM

AFM images was clicked to study the topographical shape of alone and drug encapsulated metallic nanoparticle. The images clearly indicate that the fabricated drug

encapsulated nanoparticles are almost round in shape with the measurement of 22.5nm and 55nm for zinc oxide and copper oxide nanoparticles. (figure 6).

Figure 6 AFM scan of metallic nano-medicine

2.1.6. TGA-DSC

TGA- DSC coupled instrument was used to study the purity of the synthesized drug encapsulated metallic nanoparticles as compare to the model drug. The DSC spectra of the LED drug shows a weak exothermic peak at a temperature of $165\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ corresponding to the melting of the drug which is

slightly lower than the reported value due to the presence of drug in to the amorphous form. Whereas, after the drug encapsulation to ZnNPs DSC curve shows a very

strong endothermic peak predicting the highest purity of the synthesized drug encapsulated ZnNPs. TGA curve shows that the LED start to decompose at 164 °C and after the drug encapsulation to CuNPs a strong exothermic peak appears at 410 °C which is clearly predicted the

thermal sustainability is getting enhanced significantly (figure 7). The kinetic parameters were calculated by Horowitz-Metzger equation by which activation energy was found to be 46.43, 64.20 and 43.20 KJ/mol for LED and drug encapsulated CuNPs and ZnNPs respectively.

Figure 7 TGA-DSC spectra of LED and metallic nano-medicine

3. Conclusion

The present study successfully fabricates and characterizes the nano-medicine of antiviral drug i.e. ledipasvir in which biological metal ions (zinc and copper) have been used with good drug encapsulation percentage of the model drug. These metallic nano-medicine designs to enhance the strength, sustainability and purity of the drug moiety and also reduce the chances of developing drug resistance against the virus.

Conflict of Interest

Author declares no conflict of interest.

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